

Data Management Plan

Deliverable D6.2

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TRANSPATH

Transformative pathways for synergising just biodiversity and climate actions

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Summary

The Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement requires that a data management plan (DMP) is established and regularly updated. This DMP describes how research data are managed both throughout the lifecycle of the project and after the end of the project. It identifies procedures and minimum requirements to collect, store, analyse, and publish data in a consistent way according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles.

This document is a living document and will be regularly updated when necessary. Milestones are scheduled for M24 and a final report on M48. All project partners will be informed of the changes made to this document via the project Steering Group meetings and made available via the internal information processes and during the meeting of the next General Assembly.

The basis for this document is the Horizon template for a Data Management Plan [1].

List of abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
EEAB	External Expert Advisory Board
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
RCTs	Randomized Controlled Trials
TRANSPATH	Transformative pathways for synergising just biodiversity and climate actions
WR	Wageningen Research
WU	Wageningen University
WUR	Wageningen University and Research

List of participants

Partner No.	Participant	Country
1	Wageningen University (WU)	Netherlands
2	Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences (CG)	Czechia
3	Helmholtz Center for Environmental Research (UFZ)	Germany
4	Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving (PBL)	Netherlands
5	Centro Agronómico Tropical de Investigación y Enseñanza (CATIE)	Costa Rica
6	Sustainabilogy (SU) - JD Tàbara	Spain
7	University of Ghana (ISSER)	Ghana
8	Wageningen Research (WR)	Netherlands
9	Pensoft Publishers (PEN)	Bulgaria
10	University of Geneva (UNIGE)	Switzerland
11	World Resources Institute-Africa (WRI-Africa), International	Netherlands
12	University College London (UCL)	United Kingdom

1 Data summary

TRANSPATH aims to use an inclusive deliberative process to identify context-specific leverage points and associated interventions that create enabling conditions. These are needed to accelerate diverse transformative pathways for mutually influencing extraction, production, and consumption that jointly enhance biodiversity, climate mitigation and climate adaptation, with sensitivity to different social-cultural contexts and rights.

Key result areas are:

- (1) to set up an External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) and Science-policy-practitioner Labs at multiple scales;
- (2) to identify and characterise leverage points for diverse contexts;
- (3) to integrate and customise European/global pathways by considering coupled biodiversity-climate actions and critical leverage points; and
- (4) to identify and test alternative interventions at global and European scales that can trigger transformative change at the level of consumers, producers and organisations.

To achieve these results, the project focuses on five cases: (1&2) Eastern and Western European cases reflecting the differential socio-economic and ecological conditions and challenges faced by these contexts; (3) Global trade agreements and trade regulations; (4) EU financial sector; and (5) teleconnected global value chain regulations and effects on land and forest protection/restoration.

This section describes the types of data that will be collected, processed and generated within the project by each work package accordingly (WP1-WP6).

Table 1. Data description per work package

No	Work Package name	Geographical coverage	Type of data	Methods for data gathering	Outcomes
WP1	Conceptualising leverage points and enabling conditions for transformative pathways	European	Quantitative	Review of literature	Reports, handbooks, scientific publications
WP2	Science-policy-practitioner Labs for co-designing transformative pathways	European, with respect to the Western European and Eastern European context	Research data: Quantitative; Qualitative External data	Secondary data Open data Surveys Interviews Focus groups Workshops	Data files, maps, infographics, tables, pictures, videos, reports, handbooks, scientific publications
WP3	Pathway interactions at European and global level	European and global level	Research data: Quantitative; Qualitative External data	Secondary data; Open data	Data files, maps, infographics, tables, pictures, videos, reports, handbooks, scientific publications, databases
WP4	Interventions to trigger and accelerate just and synergised biodiversity-climate transformative pathways	European and global level	Research data: Quantitative; Qualitative External data	Secondary data Open data Surveys Interviews Workshops Focus groups	Data files; Audio files; handbooks, scientific publications
WP5	Dissemination, outreach and catalysing transformative pathways	European and global level	Personal data	Cookies, server data, Google Analytics, Sendinblue	Project website and newsletter
WP6	Project management, coordination and science and policy interface	European and global level	Research data: Quantitative; Qualitative	Interviews, Workshops	Data files, maps, infographics, tables, pictures, videos, reports, handbooks, scientific publications

1.1 Data categories

Three main categories of data have been identified from the table 1:

Figure 1: Type of data categories and examples

1.1.1 Research data

The research data in this project is quantitative and qualitative data originating from the project activities such as surveys, focus groups, stakeholder meetings and interviews. Management of research data will be done in accordance with the related guidelines governing scientific research, such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity [2], the Guidelines to rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications & Open Access to Research Data in Horizon Europe [3], and the Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon Europe [1].

New data will be collected through surveys online, either via e.g. Qualtrics or o-Tree, and the implementation of Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs). The data will be analysed in either Stata or R. Stata do-files and R scripts will be uploaded to an online repository, such as git.wur.nl. Documentation on the experimental design and procedures, definitions of variables, etc. will be added to the dataset and as a ReadMe file, in both TXT format and as a Stata or R code to properly label variables. For the updated version of the data management plan, we aim to consider more common formats, such as RDF, to improve reuse of research data and achieve semantic interoperability.

New data will also be collected through interviews and/or workshops/focus groups. These files will be transcribed and anonymized. Microsoft Word will be used to analyse text based information. Photos and notes from workshops will be saved in digital images and stored as JPEGs.

Since this will involve personal data, special attention is required with respect to the anonymisation of personal data and limitation of public access. For wider publication, data will be abstracted so that core messages can be communicated, not revealing sensitive data. Due to the sensitive data that will be managed during the project, it is scheduled to request a total or partial opting-out of some specific data in accordance with existing rules concerning the protection of personal data in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Further details are given in Deliverable D6.5 – Guidelines on Ethics and Security.

1.1.2 External data

External data is mainly open data sets that are accessible to the public and can also be used in this project. These can be data aggregated form, for example weather data, satellite data, economic data. External, open data does not require data management in the sense of privacy or sensitivity. However, careful attention will be paid to the different licences for open data that could limit certain use of data.

At this stage of the project we do not know all the databases. Examples of potential databases are:

- The SSP, CD-LINKS, GEA, and IPCC AR6 scenario databases hosted by: <https://iiasa.ac.at/models-tools-data>
- The IEA scenarios databases: <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/data-sets>
- The IMAGE scenarios data output provided by PBL: <https://models.pbl.nl/image/index.php/Download>
- The GSG scenarios quantification, provided by: <https://www.tellus.org/cgi-bin/scenarios/sds.cgi>

1.1.3 Meta data

Meta data are defined as data that describe one or more aspects of the data. Metadata is increasingly getting more important to be able to share data in a meaningful way. Therefore, data categories, like research data, need to be described with meta data to ensure reuse. Per data set, metadata, such as keywords, will be provided by the data collector to optimize the possibility for discovery and potential re-use in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed. Anonymised or pseudonymised data that will be made public needs to be compliant with GDPR [4], [5]. Metadata is a central component of the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.

2 FAIR data

A FAIR approach [6], [7] will be adopted as a general guiding principle for the collection, processing, and sharing of data during the implementation of the TRANSPATH project. According to the FAIR approach, data will be collected and stored in a form that guarantees that data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

Box 1. The Fair Guiding Principles [6]
<p>To be Findable:</p> <p>F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.</p> <p>F2. data are described with rich metadata.</p> <p>F3. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.</p> <p>F4. metadata specify the data identifier.</p>
<p>To be Accessible:</p> <p>A1 (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.</p> <p>A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.</p> <p>A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.</p> <p>A2 metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.</p>
<p>To be Interoperable:</p> <p>I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</p> <p>I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.</p> <p>I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.</p>
<p>To be Re-usable</p> <p>R1. (meta)data have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.</p> <p>R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.</p> <p>R1.2. (meta)data are associated with their provenance.</p> <p>R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards</p>

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The generated data will be well-documented, and they will have clear license and provenance information. Concerning the documentation, a README file for ensuring that the data can be correctly interpreted and re-analysed by others will be created as a starting point. For the next phases of the project (especially at the end) the readme file should be replaced with metadata entered in other systems, such as yoda.wur.nl, fairdatapoint.org as considered platforms.

README file will include:

- a) a short description of what data it includes along with tables, figures, or sections;
- b) for tabular data: definitions of column headings and row labels, data codes (including missing data) and measurement units;
- c) any data processing steps that may affect interpretation of results;
- d) a description of what associated datasets are stored elsewhere, if applicable and
- e) contact information.

A README file is a document that accompanies the data and provides an explanation of the data, making the data understandable and reusable. A template and an explanation for making a README file is available at WUR [8].

For the provision of code at partners like UFZ use Gitlab [9] and for geodata use GeoNetwork [10]. Furthermore WUR provides git.wur.nl. These will be considered and the selected tools and platforms will be chosen for the next update of the project M24.

2.2 Making data accessible

Repositories also enable data accessibility. Data may be archived publicly or with restricted/closed access.

At the time of preparation of the present report open repositories for sharing data have not already been set up. A preliminary repository for data collected and instrumental to the preparation of project deliverables has been prepared by WUR, based on Sharepoint technology. The repository is accessible to the consortium of the project and is used to support collaboration among partners. All partners, according to the specific data collected and processed, will use repositories that are made accessible. The partners will follow the procedures to describe data that will be used in order to ensure long-term preservation of the data sets. Information on available data sets, repositories, and procedures to access data will be communicated via the TRANSPATH project website. Some tools that are considered as repositories in a later stage of the project are yoda.wur.nl and iRods. The internal WUR library and data office will be consulted.

Data will be stored in a separate data usage tracker that allows to document meta data (e.g., the type of data, origin), its storage place and the parties granted to it. This will also specifically include if the data is intended for publication as open access data. The data and will be archived during the project of 4 years and after, for the duration of an additional 10 years.

The general principles for handling Knowledge and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) within TRANSPATH have been settled in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement (CA). These principles are in line with Horizon Europe IPR recommendations. Background and foreground (results) will be clearly identified in detail within the consortium agreement and when applicable, granting of access rights will be clearly specified.

2.3 Making data interoperable

Data is interoperable when accessed and processed from multiple sources without losing meaning and integrating that data for mapping, visualization, and other forms of representation and analysis [11]. All data files in the project (raw data, processed data, code etc.) used in data collection, processing, and analysis should be made interoperable as much as possible.

The produced data will use common formats and standards and community agreed schemas, controlled vocabularies, keywords, thesauri or ontologies where possible in order to be interoperable and be integrated with other data, applications and workflows.

Where applicable, data will include qualified references to other data (from the project, or datasets from previous research).

To improve interoperability, standard ontologies and accepted metadata standards, such as RDF, SKOS and OWL, will be applied in project implementation, with specific attention to aligning with key knowledge platforms.

2.4 Increase data re-use

The use of Open Access, non-licenced software will be applied to ensure reuse of data. TRANSPATH reports will be licensed under Creative Commons license [12]. In general, data produced in the project will be made openly available as soon as the related deliverables are uploaded in the Project Portal. Specific arrangements are specified in the CA. The CA of the project states that the consortium partners shall, where necessary, conclude a separate data

processing, data sharing and/or joint controller agreement before any data processing or data sharing takes place.

3 Other research outputs

Other outputs of the project, such as digital outputs (e.g., software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical outputs (e.g., new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) will be monitored by the project team, by asking for specific other formats during Periodic reporting. Also, methodologies for stakeholder engagement, if openly accessible, can be shared via selected repositories.

4 Allocation of resources

In general, each Work Package leader is responsible for the data sets that are used for the Monitoring System and / or for research during the project. This responsibility can be delegated to the Task leader or researcher responsible for data collection; the data collector. The project management team is available for support. Any changes in this responsibility can be listed in the DMP per research activity.

Due to centralized support processes within WUR, it is expected that data management will not lead to extra cost for the project. If any costs for data curation and storage/preservation will be incurred, the DMP will be updated, and costs will be processed as material cost as part of Work Package 6 Project Coordination.

5 Data security

Data security is in place using the project collaboration platform MS Teams which is hosted on the WUR network. Specific partners also have protocols to archive research data generated and processed within the duration of the project.

WUR provides an overview of permitted storage options for research and non-research data storage. The most suitable storage location depends on factors such as data type, size, retention, access rights, etc. Using a new Data Storage Finder, researchers can find the most adequate storage location for their data [13]. Further details are given in Deliverable D6.5 – Guidelines on Ethics and Security.

For example WUR offers a range of IT solutions to host and manages research data, such as W:Drive, [Yoda](#) and MS Teams. For the project, data security is in place using the project collaboration platform MS Teams which is hosted on the WUR network. WUR checks whether systems or services meet the safety requirements of a specific classification. ApprovedApps is [published](#) within WUR and accessible by everyone wanting to check whether a system meets the requirements for their data set.[14]

Concerning repositories to publish processed data, we would likely use international repositories such as iRods and [Yoda](#) on the WUR servers. Other archives like Zenodo would be considered.[15] The updated version of this document will include more background, criteria and selection of tools to collect, use, store, publish and archive data in a FAIR and secure way.

6 Ethics

The consortium will comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016). The GDPR has been analysed and reviewed in order to align the project objectives accordingly. All partners should have their internal procedures updated and are compliant with current legislation. To be sure that partners comply, a compliance check may be organised asking the partners to confirm compliance.

Involvement of stakeholders, end users and the linked feedback and participatory processes are very important within this project. This includes aspects where ethical and gender issues must be checked (e.g., the selection of stakeholders, their consent for participation in the experiments, data privacy and protection). In line with the ethics self-assessment, actions will be executed for involvement of humans and for the protection of personal data.

During the project, and for a period after its completion (as per Consortium Agreement), partners will preserve the confidentiality of any data, documents or other material. Further details are given in Deliverable D6.5 – Guidelines on ethics and security.

7 Next steps

The next versions of the Data Management Plan (DMP) will be developed according to the deliverable deadlines. An overview of expected changes is displayed below in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Data Management Plan development timeline

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